

COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY INDICATORS OF HOSIERY PRODUCTS

Jurabayev Nozimjon Nizomiddin o'g'li

Namangan State Technical University, PhD student,
Phone:+998939433123, Email:jnozimjon96@gmail.com

Yusupov Sabirjon Abdujabborovich

Namangan State Technical University, Docent
Phone:+998939278728

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759776>

Abstract. In this article, a comprehensive evaluation diagram was formed by studying the physical and mechanical properties of hosiery products with different compositions and recommendations were made to manufacturing enterprises for samples with the highest quality indicators.

Keywords: comprehensive assessment, hosiery products, air permeability, water absorption, spandex

Introduction. Comprehensive assessment of the quality indicators of hosiery products is of great importance in the modern textile industry. With increasing market demands, consumers are paying attention not only to the appearance of the product, but also to its comfort, durability and aesthetic properties. Based on this, the development of scientifically based approaches to comprehensively analyze the quality of hosiery products, determine its main indicators and evaluate them is one of the current issues.

In a comprehensive assessment of product quality, analyses are carried out on individual and generalized indicators. This process covers the physical and mechanical properties of hosiery products - such indicators as air permeability, water absorption, tensile strength, resistance to deformation and friction. A comprehensive assessment also shows whether the product meets the requirements of international and national standards and the level of quality based on consumer requirements.

The integrated use of modern scientific approaches, instrumental, organoleptic, expert and differential methods allows for a comprehensive assessment of the quality of socks. The results of such analysis serve as the basis for improving the quality management system in product production and creating competitive goods.

Experimental part. During the research, samples of 4 different compositions were obtained on a single-needle 156-needle sock knitting machine of the Chinese company Kejun, model KJ6F606, installed in the "Nam

Inno tex Techno” technopark of Namangan State Technical University, and their technological indicators and physical and mechanical properties were studied.

Composition of samples

Table 1

N ^o	Samples
1	100% cotton
2	90% cotton 10% spandex
3	80% cotton 20% spandex
4	80% cotton 10% spandex 10% polyester

In the production of samples, 35 tex cotton yarn was used, and the rubber part was made of 110 d rubber, 100 d polyester and 30/75 d spandex yarn. Initially, taking into account the fact that cotton yarn has better air permeability and water absorption properties than artificial and synthetic yarns, we developed socks from 100% cotton, aiming to improve the quality of the socks and have a positive effect on human health. Then, taking into account the shape retention and deformation properties, we developed socks samples in the remaining percentages and tested their physical and mechanical properties at the “Textile Products Testing Laboratory” of Namangan State Technical University.

Physical and mechanical characteristics of hosiery products

Table 2

Indicators		Options				Standarts
		I	II	III	IV	
Yarn type and linear density		100% cotton	90% cotton 10% spandex	80% cotton 20% spandex	80% cotton 10% spandex 10% polyester	
Air permeability V(sm ³ /sm ² ·sec)		49	40	32	28,5	GOST 12088-7730 -100
Breaking strength R (N)	height	214	225	192	295	GOST 28554
	width	102	233	93	269	
Stretching until breaking L (%)	height	47	100,4	113,6	97,9	GOST 28554

	width	132,2	181,4	96,6	145,1	
Irreversible deformation ε_n (%)	heigh t	14	16	13	15	GOST 28882-90
	width	18	20	17	19	
Reversible deformation ε_o (%)	heigh t	86	84	87	85	GOST 28882-90
	width	82	80	83	81	
Abrasion resistance I (thousands of revolutions)		30	34	36	39	GOST 16486-93

To determine the quality options of hosiery products, a complex assessment diagram of quality indicators was used. The diagram presents the results of the analysis of the quality of hosiery products in graphical form. The complex diagram graph is constructed as follows: its outer contour indicates that knitted fabrics have a high quality indicator. That is, the closer the contour is to the outside, the higher the quality of the knitted fabrics and the closer they are to the requirements.

- I —————
- III —————
- II —————
- IV —————

Figure 1. Comprehensive evaluation diagram of the obtained samples

The results obtained from the technological indicators and physical and mechanical properties of knitted fabrics presented in the tables were used to construct diagrams and calculate the area of polygons.

Conclusion. On each axis of the complex diagram, numerical indicators of the results of technological indicators and physical and mechanical properties of mixed hosiery products are placed. In this case, their best indicators are drawn on the outer contour: the largest for positive indicators and the smallest for negative indicators. This diagram shows the physical and mechanical indicators necessary for hosiery products and affecting hygienic indicators. According to it, it can be seen that in variants I and III, air permeability is better than in the other two samples. The deformation index also reached a high level in these samples, which led to an improvement in shape retention.

List of references:

1. <https://srcyrl.betopsocksfactory.com/info/the-history-of-socks-101992580.html>
2. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trikotaj_sanoati
3. Jurabayev.N.N, Shogofurov.Sh.Sh, Kholikov.K.M, Meliboev.U.X (2021). Study of the fabric structure influence on the physical-mechanical and technological properties of knitted products. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 304, p. 03030). EDP Sciences.
4. D.Sponsor, Comprehensive handbook of knitting technology. Textbook – USA Woodhead Publishing LTD 2001-386 p
5. N.R.Xanxadjaeva. “Naqsh hosil qilish nazariy asoslari” Toshkent. 2010 yil.
6. N.Jurabayev, S.Yusupov, Sh.Shog’ofurov. Studying the physical and mechanical properties of futer knitted socks produced on a kejun sock knitting machine. To‘qimachilik va moda sanoatida ilm-fan va innovatsiyalar www.nts.uz ISSN 3030-3788
7. N.Yoqubjanov, N. Jurabayev, U. Meliboyev, Q. Xoliqov. Analysis of automated control system of flat needle knitting machines. AIP Conf. Proc. 3045, 050002 (2024)
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0197321>.
8. N. Jo’rabayev, U. Meliboyev, Q. Xoliqov. Physical Properties of Textile Fabrics AMERICAN Journal of Engineering, Mechanics and Architecture Volume 2, Issue 4, 2024 ISSN (E): 2993-2637
9. N. Jo’rabayev, U. Meliboyev. Research of technological indicators of hosiery products of different composition. “Ilm-fan va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasi: muammo va yechimlar-2023” xalqaro ilmiy anjuman.

10. N. Jo'rabayev, S. Yusupov Physiological properties of traditional and bamboo fiber hosiery products. "To'qimachilik sanoatida innovatsion texnologiyalar, ishlab chiqarishdagi muammolar tahlili hamda sohani rivojlantirish istiqbollari va moliyaviy barqarorlikni takomillashtirish" mavzusida xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman..

